

EXPLORING VARIABILITY IN PERCEPTIONS REGARDING THE IMPACT OF MOBILE PHONES ON PUPILS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE AT AGPUDLOS ELEMENTARY SCHOOL: BASIS FOR EDUCATIONAL EVALUATION

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ABSTRACT

Mobile phones have revolutionized communication and become indispensable in daily life, particularly affecting educational environments. While these devices offer unprecedented access to information and learning resources, they have sparked concerns among educators and parents regarding student distractions, diminishing attention spans, and the destruction of traditional study habits. This study investigated the effects of mobile phone usage on academic performance among pupils at Agpudlos Elementary School, explicitly examining perceptions across different demographic variables. The research employed a descriptive correlational design, utilizing surveys and questionnaires to collect data from 30 pupils. Statistical analyses, including T-tests and Levene's tests, were conducted to examine potential differences in mobile phone perception based on age, sex, and grade level. The study focused on two key dimensions: Obsessiveness and Usability. Results revealed no significant differences in pupils' perceptions regarding mobile phone obsessiveness (t -value = 0.664, p -value = 0.512, sig. = 0.527) across demographic variables. Similarly, perceptions of mobile phone usability showed no significant variations (t -value = -1.368, p -value = 0.203, sig. = 0.000), leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. These findings suggest uniformity in how pupils perceive mobile phone usage, regardless of their demographic characteristics. The study recommends developing targeted awareness programs for pupils, parents, and teachers to promote positive mobile phone usage in educational settings. Future research should explore specific interventions to maximize the educational benefits of mobile devices while minimizing their potential negative impacts on academic performance.

Keywords: *mobile phone; impacts; negative; positive; usability*

INTRODUCTION

As time passes and the world evolves, technology also advances. Alghamdi (2014) explains that technology encompasses materials, tools, techniques, and sources of power that make life easier, more enjoyable, and more efficient. Technology is growing rapidly alongside global development, offering advantages and numerous benefits to all living beings, ultimately making life more convenient.

Susilawati (2019) highlights various ways gadgets can be used, including communication, accessing global information and news, entertainment, online gaming, socializing, and forming connections with people from different regions or countries. However, along with the benefits they provide, gadgets also have disadvantages. If not used wisely, they can negatively impact users, as their services can be beneficial and harmful (Srinahyanti et al., 2019). Gadgets can be compared to a double-edged blade, as they positively and negatively impact children.

From a psychological perspective, childhood is considered a necessary and formative stage in our lives, as it is a time of learning and exploration. If children become excessively addicted to gadgets at a young age, it can potentially hinder their overall development (Sari, 2019). According to Sarwar and Soomro (2013), students have incorporated gadgets, specifically smartphones, as a routine for searching information through the internet. Whether inside or outside the classroom, smartphones and other gadgets significantly facilitate cooperation between students and teachers in the learning process.

During the pandemic of 2019-2021, the use of gadgets among children in Barangay Agpudlos, San Andres, Romblon, surged as they were confined to their homes due to lockdowns and school closures. This period marked a significant increase in children's reliance on smartphones and other devices for educational and entertainment, leading to excessive and undisciplined gadget use.

The study by Wang et al. (2023) explores the impacts of smartphone use on learning effectiveness among primary school students, revealing both positive and negative outcomes. The findings suggest that smartphones can enhance academic performance when used effectively; they may also lead to distractions and decreased motivation if mismanaged. Gila et al. (2023) found that cell phones can be a major cause of distraction during studying, noting that pupils who turned off their phones while studying performed better than those who received text messages. Even in silent mode, cell phones provide distractions that affect one's concentration capacity and provide accurate answers to challenging problems. Furthermore, excessive smartphone use among children can lead to developmental issues and decreased cognitive abilities, potentially affecting their interest in learning and academic performance (Utami, 2024).

Children cannot have unrestricted access to gadgets without their parents' permission. Munawar and Nisfah (2020) highlight that parents often perceive gadgets as "digital babysitters," using phones or other devices to keep their children occupied or well-behaved. Research by Buctot et al. (2020) highlights that 62.6% of Filipino adolescents experience smartphone addiction, with 95.5% suffering from nomophobia or the fear of being disconnected from their phones. These issues underscore the need to investigate how gadget use impacts children's health and academic performance.

Research Questions

This study focused on the effects of mobile phones on the academic performance of the selected Grade 4, 5, and 6 pupils at Agpudlos Elementary School in Barangay Agpudlos, San Andres, Romblon, which aimed to attain the following research goals:

1. To describe the demographic profile of the selected pupils in terms of:
 - a. Sex
 - b. Age
 - c. Grade Level; and
 - d. Academic Performance
2. To describe the positive effects of using mobile phones
3. To describe the adverse effects of using mobile phones
4. To describe the perception of the selected students about the use of mobile phones in terms of:
 - a. Obsessiveness; and
 - b. Usability
5. To determine the significant difference in the pupil's perception of the effect of mobile phones in terms of usability and obsessiveness.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design. A survey design that contained a quantitative research approach was employed, using a structured questionnaire as the primary source of the research instrument. Initial data was gathered regarding the perceived stressors, causes of stress, and impacts experienced by the afflicted individuals.

Research Method. The researchers used descriptive correlation using the survey and questionnaire methods. It was a research strategy that concentrated on measuring or calculating the collection and analysis of data. The researchers used this method because it emphasized objective measurement and the statistical analysis of the data that was collected through the research instrument.

Research Locale and Time of the Study. This study was conducted at Agpudlos Elementary School in Agpudlos, San Andres, Romblon. There were three selected grade

levels: Grade 4, Grade 5, and Grade 6. This study was carried out in the school year 2023-2024.

Subject and Respondents of the Study. The study involved a total of 30 respondents who were selected from Grades 4, 5, and 6. Specifically, 10 pupils were chosen from each grade level to ensure equal representation across these three grades.

Sampling Techniques. The study utilized purposive sampling, a non-probability method where researchers select participants based on their criteria. A total of 30 cellphone users were chosen through complete enumeration, ensuring that only the intended respondents were included.

Research Instrumentation. The researchers developed a survey questionnaire as their research instrument, which they created from scratch rather than adopting from previous studies. They presented the instrument to their research adviser for revisions and then had it validated by five expert validators. The questionnaire consists of two parts: the first part gathers students' profiles, including name, age, gender, and grade level, while the second part contains questions related to their studies. The researchers selected five (5) master teachers from secondary and elementary schools in the District of San Andres to validate the questionnaire. The checklist underwent a reliability test to determine the instrument's consistency based on the perception of the student responses to specific indicators of each criterion. The researchers obtained permission from the principal of Agpudlos Elementary School to conduct a survey and coordinate with the principal for data collection. After distributing questionnaires to selected students on the scheduled date, they retrieved the completed surveys an hour later to allow ample time for responses. They then analyzed the data. To assess respondents' academic performance in Grades 4 to 6, they sought permission from the respective advisers to access the final grades for the Second Quarter. All data was securely stored to protect the respondents' privacy. Tables were used to analyze the data obtained from the study.

The T-test-test Levene's test was used to assess whether there was a significant distinction between the age, sex, and grade levels of the respondents. The researchers used the following statistical treatment to analyze and determine the data gathered. The data were collected and analyzed using the t-test and Levene's test so that the researchers could assess whether there was a significant difference between pupils' perceptions of using mobile phones.

RESULTS

Table 1.1. Demographic profile of pupils in terms of age

Age	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
9 years old	9	20.0	20.0
10 years old	10	33.3	53.3
11 years old	12	40.0	93.3
12 years old	2	6.7	100.0
Total	30	100.0	

Table 1.2. Demographic profile of pupils in terms of sex

Sex	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	9	33.3	30.0
Female	21	70.0	100.0
Total	30	100.0	

Table 1.3. Demographic profile of pupils in terms of grade level

Grade Level	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Grade 4	10	33.3	33.3
Grade 5	10	33.3	66.6
Grade 6	10	33.3	100.0
Total	30	100.0	

Table 1.4. Academic Performance of 30 selected pupils during the Second Quarter in Grades 4 to Grade 6

Number of Selected Pupils	Grade 4	Descriptor	Grade 5	Descriptor	Grade 6	Descriptor
Pupil Number 1	93	O	95	O	95	O
Pupil Number 2	93	O	93	O	95	O
Pupil Number 3	90	O	90	O	93	O
Pupil Number 4	92	O	89	VS	91	O
Pupil Number 5	90	O	94	O	90	O
Pupil Number 6	89	VS	92	O	92	O
Pupil Number 7	92	O	90	O	93	O
Pupil Number 8	89	VS	94	O	92	O
Pupil Number 9	90	O	91	O	94	O
Pupil Number 10	90	O	89	VS	91	O

Legend:

90 – 100	Outstanding	75 – 79	Fairly Satisfactory
85 – 89	Very Satisfactory	Below 75	Did not Meet Expectations
80 – 84	Satisfactory		

Table 2. Factors of using mobile phones as a positive

Statement-indicator on the positive response to using mobile phones		Mean	Std. Deviation	DI
1	I can talk to my relatives in faraway places using cell phones.	2.93	0.37	A
2	Using a cell phone makes it easier to access information.	2.77	0.63	A
3	It makes my life easier when answering schoolwork	2.77	0.63	A
4	I can immediately call for help using my cellphone if I am in danger.	2.73	0.64	A
5	I use my cellphone for relaxation and entertainment.	2.10	0.88	DA
Average Weighted Mean-Perception		2.66	0.63	A
Legend:	Descriptive Interpretation	(DI)		
3.51 – 4.00	Strongly Agree	(SA)		
2.51 – 3.50	Agree	(A)		
1.51 – 2.50	Disagree	(DA)		
1.00 – 1.50	Strongly Disagree	(SDA)		

Table 3. Factors of using mobile phones as a negative

Statement-indicator on adverse effects of using mobile phone		Mean	Std. Deviation	DI
1	Using my phone distracts my focus on schoolwork	2.00	0.83	DA
2	I spent most of my allowance on buying a load	1.90	0.55	DA
3	I find it difficult to stop using cell phones.	1.83	0.7	DA
4	I already have posture issues using my cellphone	1.73	0.64	DA
5	I spend less time socializing with others	1.73	0.58	DA
Average Weighted Mean-Perception		1.84	0.66	DA
Legend:	Descriptive Interpretation	(DI)		
3.51 – 4.00	Strongly Agree	(SA)		
2.51 – 3.50	Agree	(A)		
1.51 – 2.50	Disagree	(DA)		
1.00 – 1.50	Strongly Disagree	(SDA)		

Table 4.1. Responses of pupils about the use of mobile phones in terms of usability

Statement-indicator on mobile phones in terms of usability	Mean	Std. Deviation	DI
1 I use dictionaries on my phone to check the words I am not familiar with during class hours.	3.63	0.56	SA
2 I use my phone as a calculator.	3.17	0.87	A
3 I use my phone as an alarm clock to wake up early in the morning.	3.17	0.91	A
4 I use my phone to take photos of our lesson.	3.13	1.01	A
5 I read online books through my phone.	2.83	0.95	A
6 I use my mobile phone to search for funny and interesting videos.	2.77	1.01	A
7 I spend 2-3 hours browsing the internet while doing my schoolwork.	2.73	0.78	A
8 I use my phone to share ideas with my classmates.	2.60	1.13	A
9 I have failing grades because of my mobile phone.	1.90	0.8	DA
10 I use my phone to cheat during tests inside the class.	1.33	0.55	SDA
Average Weighted Mean-Perception	2.73	0.86	A

Legend: Descriptive Interpretation (DI)
3.51 – 4.00 Strong Agree (SA)
2.51 – 3.50 Agree (A)
1.51 – 2.50 Disagree (DA)
1.00 – 1.50 Strongly Disagree (SDA)

Table 4.2. Responses of pupils about the use of mobile phones in terms of Obsessiveness

Statement-indicator on mobile phones in terms of Obsessiveness	Mean	Std. Deviation	DI
1 I can relieve my stress when I am using my phone.	2.43	0.90	DA
2 I spend 2-3 hours playing games on my mobile phone.	2.27	0.94	DA
3 I feel dizzy after I use my phone.	2.23	0.94	DA
4 I opened my phone first instead of answering my assignment.	1.97	0.96	DA
5 I use my mobile phone for 2-3 hours a day.	1.90	0.84	DA
6 I prefer to spend my time using a mobile phone instead of going out with my friends.	1.90	0.84	DA
7 I spend the whole weekend playing games on my mobile phone.	1.87	0.73	DA
8 I sleep late at night because of my mobile phone.	1.70	0.84	DA
9 I use my mobile phone while eating.	1.53	0.73	DA
10 I skip meals while playing online games.	1.37	0.61	SDA
Average Weighted Mean-Perception	1.97	0.83	DA

Legend: Descriptive Interpretation (DI)
3.51 – 4.00 Strong Agree (SA)
2.51 – 3.50 Agree (A)

1.51 – 2.50 Disagree (DA)
 1.00 – 1.50 Strongly Disagree (SDA)

Table 5. Differences in the perception of pupils on the effect of mobile phones in terms of usability and Obsessiveness

Variables		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means			Result	Decision
		F	Sig.	t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed) (p)		
1 Usability of Mobile Phone	Equal variances not assumed	16.477	0.000	-1.368	9.319	0.203	Not Significant	Accept Ho
2 Obsessiveness on Mobile Phone	Equal variances assumed	0.41	0.527	0.664	27	0.512	Not Significant	Accept Ho

DISCUSSION

The data presented in Table 1.1 offers a detailed breakdown of the respondents' ages, shedding light on the distribution within the sample. The percentages provided indicate the proportion of respondents falling within different age categories. According to Table 2.1, the age distribution of the respondents is segmented into four categories: 9 years, 10 years, 11 years, and 12 years. The percentages of each category indicate the proportion of respondents within that specific age range. Among the respondents, 20% are reported to be 9 years old, 33.3% are 10, 40% are 11, and 6.7% are 12. These percentages provide a comprehensive view of the age distribution within the respondent pool. The statement highlights that most respondents who use mobile phones and participated in the questionnaire fall within the age of 11, constituting the majority with 40%. This suggests that the age group of 11 years old has the highest representation among the respondents.

The information in Table 1.2 describes the gender distribution of the respondents who use mobile phones. The percentages provided offer insights into the sample composition in terms of male and female respondents. Table 1.2 provides a breakdown of the respondents based on their gender. The data shows 33.3% of the respondents are male, while 70% are female. The percentages reveal the proportion of male and female respondents within the sample. The relatively higher percentage for females indicates a

more excellent representation of female respondents who use mobile phones and participated in the study. The statement emphasizes that most of the respondents using mobile phones are composed of females, as the female respondents constitute a significant majority with a percentage of 70%. This gender distribution is important to consider when analyzing and interpreting the study's findings, as it may contribute to gender-specific insights into mobile phone usage patterns and behaviors.

The information provided in Table 1.3 outlines the researchers' selection criteria for participants in the study. The focus is on pupils from different grade levels (specifically grade 4, 5, and 6) who use mobile phones to answer the questionnaire. Table 1.3 indicates that the researchers specifically targeted pupils who use mobile phones to participate in the study. The selection is further narrowed down to include pupils from grade 4, grade 5, and grade 6. According to the information, the researchers selected 10 pupils from the mentioned grade levels—grade 4, grade 5, and grade 6. Consequently, the total number of pupils selected for the study is 30 (10 pupils from each grade level)

Table 1.4 displays the academic Performance of 30 students across three grade levels during the second quarter. Most notably, 26 out of 30 students achieved "Outstanding" Performance, with only 4 receiving "Very Satisfactory" marks. Grade 6 showed a particularly strong performance, with all students achieving "Outstanding" grades ranging from 90% to 95%.

Table 2 shows the positive effect of mobile phones. The research findings revealed significant positive effects of mobile phones on pupils' daily lives. Based on the results, students agreed that mobile phones help them communicate with relatives in faraway places, scoring the highest mean of 2.97. Following this, students equally valued mobile phones for accessing information and completing schoolwork, earning a mean score of 2.77. Safety was another important benefit, with students agreeing (mean of 2.73) that mobile phones allow them to immediately call for help in dangerous situations. Interestingly, students disagreed with the statement that mobile phones help them relax and stay entertained, as indicated by the lowest mean score of 2.10. Overall, with a total average weighted mean of 2.66, the respondents generally agreed that mobile phones positively affect their lives, particularly for practical purposes rather than entertainment. A similar finding, like Setiawati et al. (2018), highlights that, in line with Handriano's findings, using mobile phones in early childhood has positive impacts. These include fostering imagination, enhancing intelligence, boosting self-confidence, and facilitating reading, mathematics, and problem-solving development.

From Table 3, it presents the negative effects of mobile phone. The research findings on the negative effects of mobile phones among pupils revealed that students generally disagreed with statements suggesting adverse impacts. Students most strongly disagreed (mean of 2.00) with the notion that mobile phones distracted them from their schoolwork. They also disagreed with the statement about spending most of their allowance on mobile phone load (mean of 1.90) and rejected the idea that they had difficulty stopping their phone usage (mean of 1.83). Additionally, pupils disagreed equally (with a mean of 1.73) with claims about developing posture issues from phone use and

less socializing with others. With an average weighted mean of 1.84, the results indicate that pupils generally did not perceive significant negative effects from mobile phone use, suggesting they maintain healthy boundaries with their devices.

Table 4.1 represents the mobile phone in terms of usability. The research findings on mobile phone usability among Grade 4, 5, and 6 pupils at Agpudlos Elementary School revealed diverse usage patterns. The study found that pupils used their mobile phones most frequently as educational tools, with dictionary usage during class hours scoring the highest mean of 3.63. Calculator functions and alarm clock features tied for the second-highest mean of 3.17, indicating regular use of these practical applications. Students also agreed that they used their phones to take lessons (mean of 3.13) and read books (mean of 2.83). Entertainment and communication aspects were moderately utilized, with students agreeing they searched for funny and interesting videos (mean of 2.77), spent 2-3 hours browsing the internet while doing schoolwork (mean of 2.73), and shared ideas with classmates (mean of 2.60). Notably, students strongly disagreed with negative academic impacts, as indicated by their disagreement with experiencing failing grades due to mobile phone use (mean of 1.90) and their strong disagreement with using phones for cheating during tests (mean of 1.33). With an average weighted mean of 2.73, the findings suggest that pupils generally use their mobile phones responsibly and primarily for educational purposes

From the Table 4.2, the table reveals about the mobile phone in terms of Obsessiveness. The research examining mobile phone obsessiveness among Grade 4, 5, and 6 pupils at Agpudlos Elementary School revealed that students generally maintained healthy boundaries with their device usage. The findings showed that pupils disagreed with most statements suggesting obsessive behavior, starting with the highest mean of 2.43 for using phones to relieve stress. Students also disagreed that they spent 2-3 hours playing mobile games (mean 2.27) or experienced dizziness after phone use (mean 2.23). More notably, they disagreed with prioritizing phone use over homework (mean of 1.97), using phones for 2-3 hours daily (mean of 1.90), and choosing phone time over socializing with friends (also mean of 1.90). The lowest levels of agreement were found in potentially problematic behaviors, with students disagreeing that they spent entire weekends playing mobile games (mean of 1.87), lost sleep due to phone use (mean of 1.70), used phones while eating (mean of 1.53), or skipped meals to play online games (lowest mean of 1.37). The overall average weighted mean of 1.97 indicates that pupils demonstrate responsible mobile phone usage patterns and do not exhibit significant signs of phone addiction or obsessive behavior.

The table 5 presents the significant difference on the perception of pupils on the effect of mobile phone in terms of usability and Obsessiveness. The analysis of the usability of mobile phones indicates a significant difference in variances between groups (p -value = 0.000), violating the assumption of equal variances. However, the subsequent t -test (t -value = -1.368, p -value = 0.203) does not provide enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis. The negative t -value suggests a potential lower mean in the first group, but this difference is not statistically significant. Consequently, no strong evidence supports a significant difference in usability between the groups based on the collected data.

Similarly, in the context of Obsessiveness related to mobile phones, the assumption of equal variances is met (p-value = 0.527). The t-test (t-value = 0.664, p-value = 0.512) indicates no significant difference in means between groups. The positive t-value suggests a potential slightly higher mean in the first group, but this difference is not statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted, and there is no compelling evidence to suggest a significant difference in Obsessiveness based on the collected data.

Conclusions

Considering the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. In terms of sex, it is emphasizing a higher representation of females among mobile phone users in the study than males. In terms of age, it categorizes them into four groups: 9 years, 10 years, 11 years, and 12 years, where 11 years has the highest number of participants and 12 years old is the lowest. In terms of grade level, the study focuses on pupils from grades 4, 5, and 6 who use mobile phones, 10 pupils were selected from each grade level, resulting in a total of 30 participants for the study. In terms of academic performance, all respondents met the standard passing rate.
2. Based on the findings of the study on the factors of using a mobile phone as a positive, it appears that many of the pupils agree that I can talk to my relatives in faraway places using a cellphone; using a cellphone makes it easier for me to access information, it makes life easier when answering schoolwork, I can immediately call for help using cellphone if I am in danger and disagree with I use my cellphone for relaxation and entertainment.
3. the study's findings on the factors of using a mobile phone as a negative reveal that most pupils disagree with all the statement indicators.
4. The study revealed two key findings regarding mobile phone use among pupils. In terms of Obsessiveness, students generally disagreed with most indicators suggesting addictive behavior, with firm disagreement about using phones during meals. Regarding usability, pupils strongly agreed that they used their phones as educational tools, especially for dictionary functions during class. They also agreed with using phones for practical purposes like calculations, alarms, photo-taking of lessons, reading online books, watching videos, internet browsing for schoolwork, and sharing ideas with classmates. Notably, students disagreed with statements suggesting academic misconduct, such as using phones for cheating or experiencing failing grades due to phone use.
5. There is no significant difference between pupils' perceptions of using mobile phones in terms of Obsessiveness and usability. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the research, the researchers have provided the following recommendations:

1. Regardless of sex, age, grade level, and academic performance, pupils may use mobile phones with the guidance of their teachers and parents.
2. Teachers may incorporate mobile devices into their instructional methods, recognizing the potential benefits they can bring to the educational environment.
3. Recognizing the growing influence of mobile phones and digital devices in pupils' lives, schools may increasingly be proactive in conducting related training and workshops to educate pupils about their proper use. These initiatives are designed to impart essential digital literacy skills and foster responsible and mindful use of technology among pupils.
4. The study should be put forward, and more work should be implemented on self-efficacy and behavioral intention and their impact on student's academic performance when using mobile phones.
5. The study may benefit pupils, parents, and teachers by facilitating their students' training and guidance to spread awareness regarding the positive usage of mobile phones.
6. Future researchers may add more variables to this favorable topic to examine the overall impact of mobile phones.

These recommendations highlight the potential benefits of using mobile phones in enhancing proper usage and promoting effective awareness regarding the impact of mobile phones.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The pupils and respondents were informed about the details of the study. The researchers informed parents or guardians to allow their children to participate in this research study through a letter of consent or waiver. The researchers assured that all the collected data was valid and reliable, treated with the utmost confidentiality, and only used in this study.

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